

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CULTURE OF THE MEDIEVAL RENAISSANCE PERIOD

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Annotation: This article analyzes the characteristics of the culture of the Italian Renaissance, the development of medieval history, and its similarities and connections with the culture of the Eastern Renaissance, and comments on the scientific activity of medieval scholars.

Keywords: Italy, Renaissance, Florence, “History of Florence”, ruler, government, city, tyranny, Renaissance, Eastern Renaissance, political order, church

Studying the activities of our thinkers who made a great contribution to the development of world science, in-depth research of the importance of the rich scientific heritage they left, plays an important role in the deeper assimilation of the cultural and scientific history of this country, in the formation of national ideology and consequently, in raising the spiritual potential of the people. In addition, such researches are considered one of the main and necessary directions in terms of the historiography of international scientific relations, as well as from the perspective of source studies.

Historical sources show that the life of Renaissance thinkers in Italy is one of the most complicated historical problems. Because the lives of these scientists have not yet been fully covered. The information provided is not complete. One of such historical figures is Leonardo da Vinci, many stories about his life have reached today. In addition, the manuscripts of historians and historians of that period are still the main guide for studying this period. The study of Leonardo’s life is considered one of the most important topics in the West, enigmatic questions and a philosophical riddle view of his works are still ongoing. Leonardo is considered a great scientist, inventor, painter, and sculptor of the West, and he was a prolific creator. These aspects of the scientist are revealed in each research in its own way.

In recent years, Uzbekistan’s cultural ties with Western countries, especially with Italy, have been growing. As the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, stated, “It is necessary to bring the relations with the countries of the world to a new level in terms of content and quality in the spirit of mutual friendship, good neighborliness and strategic partnership in all fields” [1].

Formation of capitalist relations in the heart of feudal society caused important changes in the life of Western Europe. Religion gradually lost its prestige, the transition from small crafts to manufacturing, the rapid expansion and development of cities, the opening of new continents and the development of trade changed the image of social life and people's attitude to life and reality.

By this time, the king's power rested on the townspeople, breaking the power of the feudal nobility and creating large-scale, essentially nation-based, monarchies. In these monarchies, modern European nations and modern bourgeois society began to develop. In the process of this development, a new secular art and culture emerged. The advent of printing made it possible for literary and scientific works to be widely disseminated. The close relations between the countries made it possible to quickly assimilate the innovations in the artistic life [2].

This new culture, which experienced its development in the 15th and 16th centuries, was named "Renaissance" in history. The expression was coined by the Italian artist and art critic George Vasari as a result of the re-awakening of art in Italy after the long Middle Ages, and was mainly applied to the work of Giotto. Later, it acquired a wider meaning and was used to describe the art that emerged in Italy and then in other European countries, which differed from the age of feudalism [3].

The culture of the Renaissance developed under the influence of the culture of the ancient world. In particular, during this period he diligently studied the monuments of the ancient times. The abundance of the monuments of the ancient world in Italy contributed to this. But the creators of this period did not become its slaves. On the contrary, they used it to describe the concepts of their thoughts and feelings.

Interest in reality and beauty became important in the development of the era. Life was recognized as a real phenomenon, and artists began to search for new rules in realistic depiction of reality. Great scientific achievements were made in the field of perspective, color science, light-shadow theory, and anatomy. Architecture and applied and decorative art served to form new trends. In particular, architects adopted ancient traditions and enriched them with new content. At the same time, new constructions of architecture were created, high-rise buildings, social buildings of a new appearance were erected. A number of achievements were also achieved in decorating the

exterior and interior of the building, and in the organization of space, which became important in the further development of European art [4].

The location of Italy on an important trade route between the East and the West led to the very early formation of capitalist relations. The development of trade and the intensity of communication with other countries created the basis for the development of handicrafts. The weakness of feudal relations allowed the emergence of a new political order, the city-republic order, and Italy was the first in Europe to be called a capitalist country. This feature, which happened in social life, found its expression in art and culture. This change was very noticeable in Florence, Pisa, Siena, located in Central Italy, where trade and production developed, and in the northern part, Genoa, Milan, and especially in Venice, a republic of merchants and bankers [5].

In many ways, today's inventions are a product of the medieval "Renaissance". Because, during this period, thinkers like Leonardo da Vinci created, and they were not limited to painting and sculpture. His creative works, covering all fields, were able to have a strong impact on certain fields such as construction, mechanics, and aquaponics. His ideas were incomparable and very relevant.

To sum up, while studying the history of the Renaissance, we are faced with many valid questions, and in finding these questions, we get entangled in a series of confusions or doubts. The reasons for a series of questions that cause vague ideas remain hidden in Leonardo's 7 thousand drawings and paintings. By studying the culture of the Renaissance in more depth, we can get relevant conclusions about the achievements of science of that time.

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